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Five Years Experience in Performing Abdominoplasty and Posterior Colpoperineorrhaphy in One Operative Session

Azzam Farroha,

Specialist Plastic Surgeon, Ministry of Health, Baghdad, Iraq.

asfarroha@yahoo.com

Hala Hanna,

Specialist Gynecologist, Ministry of Health, Baghdad, Iraq.

Abstract

Multiparous women might complain of both protruded and pendulous abdomens and lax vaginal outlets affecting their sexual relationship with their spouses. This series included 47 patients presented with this combined complains. Each patient underwent major abdominoplasty and posterior colpoperineorrhaphy (or perineorrhaphy) in one operative session. This approach was safe as no serious complications were reported. Also it was very convenient for patients and their families as it save time and money

Background

Abdominoplasty is a common cosmetic surgery to make a more firm abdomen by removing the excess fat and skin and tightening abdominal muscle and fascia. Abdominoplasty in women was previously combined safely and effectively with other elective surgeries such as liposuction, mammoplasty, abdominal hysterectomy, cholecystectomy, etc [1-4]. However the operation has not been reported to be combined with posterior colpoperineorrhaphy.

Many multiparous women complain of protruded and pendulous abdomen and lax vaginal outlet affecting their sexual

relationship with their spouses. These multiple complaints of the patients were classically treated by performing abdominoplasty in one operative session and posterior colpoperineorrhaphy in another session. Doing these two operations in two different operative session increases morbidity and cost; is inconvenient to patients and their families.

Patients and Methods

This case series included 47 patients, whose ages ranged from 26-54 years. All these patients complained of protruded and pendulous abdomens interfering with sexual intercourse and complained of vaginal outlet laxity reducing sexual satisfaction.

All patients were parous with average parity of 2-5, and many of them were employed (even housewives are sometimes referred to as working women). Because of their home and work responsibilities, these patients did not have enough time or funds for multiple surgeries in more than one operative session.

Table 1 showed the clinical findings. History showed that 39 patients had undergone only vaginal deliveries, 6

patients had undergone both vaginal deliveries and caesarian sections and 2 patients had undergone only caesarian sections. Sixteen patients gave history of complications of episiotomy as infection and wound dehiscence. All the patients did not perform pelvic exercises or other physical exercise after delivery properly. And all of them gained weight over time. On examination, all patients had poor skin elasticity, pendulous excess subcutaneous fat and skin below the level of anterior vulvar commissure, and lax musculoaponeurotic abdominal wall. Nine patients had also abdominal hernias, seven incisional and two lower paraumbilical hernias. All these patients had lax vaginal outlet and 32 patients also had rectocele.

Table (1): The clinical findings in the forty seven patients in this series

Clinical findings	Number of patients
Multiparous women	47
Vaginal delivery only	39
Caesarian section only	2
Vaginal delivery and caesarian section	6
Gain weight over time	47
Protruded and pendulous abdomens below the level of anterior vulvar commissure.	47
Lax musculoaponeurotic abdominal wall.	47
Paraumbilical hernias	2
Incisional hernias	7
Lax vaginal outlet	47
Rectocele	32
History of episiotomy complications as infection and wound dehiscence	16
Patients having risk factors increasing possibility of complications.	0

All these patients were checked for fitness for this combined operative

session; they did not have risk factors that might increase the possibility of complications. They did not have any conditions as ischemic heart disease, uncontrolled hypertension, diabetes, history of DVT or bleeding tendency or massive obesity and that might affect the safety of patient during long major operation. Also they did not have transverse upper abdominal scar that might affect the abdominal flap viability.

All smoker patients and smoker male partners were asked to stop smoking for one month before the surgery and at least two months after the surgery. And they were asked not to take aspirin 2 weeks before the surgery.

All patients underwent careful checking and treatment of any focus of infection, especially skin infection at abdominal folds and vaginal infection.

All the patients informed clearly that although all the surgeries were going to be in one session, this session was going to be in two steps. The first step should be used for the clean surgery in the abdomen; and the second step for the relatively contaminated surgery in the vagina. Therefore, if intra-operative complications happened while doing the first step, then the second step would be cancelled.

When the patients were admitted into the hospital, the following preoperative preparations were done:

- Bowels had been emptied by normal evacuation or by an enema [5].
- The usual perineal and vaginal preoperative preparations [5].
- Marking the abdominal midline and the anterior superior iliac spins in standing position. Then completing marking in the supine position. The

postoperative pubic hair line was marked 5-7 cm above the anterior vulvar commissure [2].

- A prophylactic dose of Heparin (5000 units) was given subcutaneously for five obese patients to avoid deep venous thrombosis. A second dose was given after 12 hours after the first one [6, 7].
- A prophylactic dose of 3rd generation of cephalosporin was given intravenously for each patients (no patient gave history of sensitivity). Then another 2 doses every 12 hours [6].

After induction of the general anesthesia, a Foley catheter was secured. The surgery started with a supine position of the patients and then semi-flex of the hip in order to complete the abdominoplasty. At the end of the first step, dressing was secured. The second part of the surgery was done in lithotomy position of the patient.

In the first step of the operative session, all the patients underwent a major abdominoplasty for repairing the lax muscles of the anterior abdominal wall, translocation of the umbilicus and resection of the excess pendulous skin and fat ⁽²⁾. Also in nine patients, the abdominal hernias were repaired.

In the second step of the surgical session, posterior colpoperineorrhaphy was performed to repair pelvic floor muscles, reconstruct perineal body, and repair the posterior vaginal wall fascia and correct rectocele [5, 8, 9, 10, 11]. The aims were to relieve symptoms, restore anatomy and functionality to normal. Thirty two patients underwent posterior colpoperineorrhaphy and fifteen patients underwent perineorrhaphy and levator placcation.

All patients were kept in the hospitals for two days. A Foley's catheter was removed the morning after surgery and gradual ambulation was started. The patients had been instructed to rest at home for one week and to gradually increase their activities in the second week. All patients returned to their usual work in the third post operative week. All patients resumed the sexual activities with their male partners in the sixth post operative week.

Results and Discussion

This team work between a gynecologist and a plastic surgeon provided excellent results for patients:

1. The combined surgical session was safe, table 2.

Table (2): Reported complications for the combined operative session

Reported complications	Number of patients
Intraoperative complications	0
Death	0
Major and serious complication of Abdominoplasty	0
Minor hematoma at left side of abdominal wound	1
Minor seroma of abdominal wound	2
Minor abdominal wound infection	1
Bilateral 'dog' ears in the abdominal scar	4
Complications of the posterior colpoperineorrhaphy	0

- a. Abdominoplasty and posterior vaginal repair were done for all patients. There were no intraoperative complications that prevent completion of both steps of the operative session.

- b. The mortality rate was zero.
 - c. All the forty seven patients did not complain of any of the serious and major complications. Literatures reported up to 16% serious and major complications such as massive blood loss, large hematoma (which required surgical intervention), large seroma (which required aspiration or surgical drainage), cellulites or abscess (which required hospitalization and intravenous antibiotic treatment), DVT, pulmonary embolism, respiratory decompensation, skin flap necrosis [2, 12, 13]. The absence of major and serious complications in this series was due to the very careful selection of patients; any patient with risk of complications was not included in this combined operative session. Also it was due to the careful preoperative preparations and postoperative monitoring and follow-up that closely supervised by the consultant.
 - d. Some of the patients complained of minor and non serious complications of the abdominoplasty:
 - i. One patient had minor hematoma at left side of abdominal wound, due to blockage of the drain at that site. No intervention required and spontaneous reabsorption occurred.
 - ii. Two patients had minor seroma of abdominal wound due to early restoration of activities in the second postoperative week and without wearing a corset or binder. No treatment required and spontaneous reabsorption occurred.
 - iii. One patient had minor abdominal wound infection surrounding two stitches; it caused a wound dehiscence of 3 cm long, which was treated conservatively.
 - iv. Four patients had bilateral 'dog' ears in the abdominal scar, which were corrected surgically under local anesthesia at about two months postoperatively.
 - e. None of the forty seven patients experienced any of the any of the complications of the posterior vaginal repair, as hematoma, wound dehiscence, infection and postoperative dyspareunia.⁽⁵⁾
2. The combined surgical session was very convenient for the patients and their families:
- a. The cost of combining the abdominoplasty and the posterior colpoperineorrhaphy in one session was about two thirds of the total cost of performing the two operations in two separate sessions. In the combined operative session, the use of major operation theater and the general anesthesia was once for each patient. The average time in the operation theater required for the combined operative session was less than the sum of doing abdominoplasty and posterior colpoperineorrhaphy in two separate sessions because there was only one time preparation of the patient and induction of general anesthesia. Hospital admission for each patient was

once and for two days only. The use of other resources during the preoperative preparation and the follow-up was for one session.

- b. The recovery time required after combining abdominoplasty and posterior colpoperineorrhaphy was about six weeks, which is the same as doing abdominoplasty alone. It was significantly less than the total recovery time required after doing the two surgeries in two separated sessions.
3. All patients and their male partners had significant improvement in their sexual relationships. The level of improvement was assessed through asking the patients to describe it as good to excellent improvements; moderate improvement; no or minimal improvements. Forty four patients reported that she and her spouse had well to excellent improvement; three patients reported moderate improvement and no patient reported no or minimal improvements. The moderate improvement of those three patients was related to the protruded pendulous abdomen of their spouses. Two of them underwent abdominoplasty and liposuction and reported later an excellent improvement.

Conclusions

- Many Multiparous women complain of problems in the sexual relationships with their spouses due to the effects of childbirth and age, leading to combination of protruded and

pendulous abdomen affecting intercourse performance and laxity of vaginal outlet affecting sexual satisfaction.

- The combined surgical session is safe for the patients; but required a careful selection of the patients; and careful preoperative preparation and postoperative monitoring and follow-up.
- The combined surgical session is very convenient for the patients and their families, because it achieves positive outcomes after a single operative session with one recovery period and less cost than doing the surgeries in multiple sessions.
- It is always useful to remember that the problems in the sexual relationships could be due to the female, male or both.
- The team work between different specialties, as in this case team work between plastic surgeon and gynecologist is very important to improve the quality of health services provided for the patients.

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